

CHARACTERISTICS OF PROSECUTORIAL SUPERVISION OVER THE IMPLEMENTATION OF LEGAL ACTS RELATED TO THE USE OF FORESTS, WATER RESOURCES, AND RESERVE LANDS

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ABSTRACT

Goal 81 of the Action Strategy on the Five Priority Directions for the Development of Our Country in 2017–2021 is titled “Expanding Forest Areas”. This goal outlines several key tasks, such as expanding forested areas in the regions of the Republic, ensuring the efficient use of forest fund lands, establishing plantations in the foothill and intermountain areas of the forest fund, increasing vegetation in desert regions, creating protective forests in various territories, and establishing shelterbelts to protect irrigated lands from erosion and to prevent sand accumulation on reclamation facilities.

Goal 81 of the Action Strategy on the Five Priority Directions for the Development of Our Country in 2017–2021 is titled “Expanding Forest Areas”. This goal outlines several key tasks, such as expanding forested areas in the regions of the Republic, ensuring the efficient use of forest fund lands, establishing plantations in the foothill and intermountain areas of the forest fund, increasing vegetation in desert regions, creating protective forests in various territories, and establishing shelterbelts to protect irrigated lands from erosion and to prevent sand accumulation on reclamation facilities. Additionally, it includes tasks such as regulating the use of forests on state forest fund lands, expanding the forest fund, organizing the protection and guarding of forests, and fundamentally revising the mechanisms for their preservation. In the State Program for the Implementation of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 during the “Year of Honoring Human Dignity and Active Neighborhood”, Priority Direction 297 outlines the following goals and tasks: Improving the legal framework for the use and protection of forest fund lands; developing the draft Forest Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan; regulating the use of forests on state forest fund lands; expanding the forest fund; improving the procedures for leasing forest fund lands, including leasing based on investment agreements or public–private partnerships; revising the management system of state forest enterprises; organizing forest enterprises; defining and adjusting land boundaries; and fundamentally reviewing the mechanisms for forest protection and preservation. According to official data, as of November 2025, forest fund lands in our Republic total 10,967,753 hectares, which accounts for 24.4% of the total land fund. Lands of residential areas (cities, urban-type settlements, and rural settlements) amount to 221,544 hectares, or 0.5% of the total land fund. Lands designated for industry, transport, communications, defense, and other purposes make up 798,778 hectares, representing 1.8% of the total land fund. Lands intended for nature

protection, health improvement, and recreation purposes comprise 4,258,751 hectares, or 9.5% of the total land fund. Lands of historical and cultural significance cover 32,320 hectares, making up 0.1% of the total land fund. Reserve lands amount to 1,351,011 hectares, or 3.0%, while water fund lands total 1,041,423 hectares, representing 2.3% of the total land fund. In our country, systematic work is being carried out to protect forests, use forest fund lands efficiently, and plant and grow trees and shrubs. The newly revised Constitution also states that land, mineral resources, water, flora and fauna, and other natural resources are national wealth, must be used wisely, and are under state protection. In addition, the Concept for the Development of the Forestry System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 has been approved, defining the strategic goals for forest protection, conservation, and the development of forestry, as well as the priority directions of state policy in this field. At the regular meeting of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis on February 6, 2024, according to the report presented by the Director of the Forestry Agency titled “On the State of Efficient Use of Forest Fund Lands,” the Law “On Forests” was adopted in a new edition. The main rules for the use of forests, particularly forest fund lands, and the powers of state bodies in this field were clarified in greater detail. Furthermore, in order to improve lease relations for the use of forest fund lands and introduce modern and transparent leasing mechanisms, the Government adopted a corresponding resolution. In 2023, the Forestry Agency carried out forest creation and reforestation measures on 235,000 hectares, and 7,012 hectares of unused forest fund land were brought into use. At the same time, measures are being taken to widely involve business entities in forestry production activities—without negatively affecting the protection and expansion of forests. At present, the issue of constructing ecotourism facilities on forest fund lands, ensuring full water supply for the trees and shrubs planted within the framework of the nationwide “Green Space” project in all settlements of our country, preserving these trees, expanding forest fund lands, increasing their forest coverage, and establishing the production of medicinal and other types of import-substituting and export-oriented products on these lands has not lost its relevance.

When organizing prosecutorial oversight over the implementation of legislation related to the use of forest fund lands, it is first necessary to clarify the subject matter of prosecutorial supervision and thoroughly study the sector-specific regulatory legal documents.

It should be noted that ensuring the efficient and rational use of the rich potential of forest resources, increasing the effectiveness of the use of forest fund lands, expanding (reconstructing) forest areas, cultivating seedlings, collecting medicinal herbs, allocating pasture lands for livestock, producing agricultural products, further improving the forest management system, introducing advanced scientific and technical achievements into the sector, strengthening and modernizing the material and technical base of forest enterprises, as well as actively attracting foreign investment and developing ecological tourism are not directly regulated by a single law or a Presidential or Cabinet of Ministers document. On 29 September 2020, the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Law No. O’Q-639 “On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan Aimed at Improving the Efficiency of the Use of Agricultural Lands and Forest Fund Lands.”

In our opinion, as a result of the adoption of this Law, the implementation of prosecutorial oversight over the enforcement of legal acts related to forest fund lands includes performing and ensuring the following organizational tasks:

First, ensuring the implementation of the tasks defined in the following documents:

– Presidential Decree No. PF-5409 of 11 April 2018 “On Measures to Further Reduce and Simplify Licensing and Permitting Procedures in Entrepreneurial Activity and Improve Business Conditions”;

– Presidential Decree No. PF-5742 of 17 June 2019 “On Measures for the Efficient Use of Land and Water Resources in Agriculture”;

– Presidential Resolution No. PQ-4424 of 23 August 2019 “On Additional Measures to Improve the Efficiency of Forest Use in the Republic”;

– Presidential Resolution No. PQ-238 of 27 July 2023 “On Accelerating Reforms in the Tourism Sector and Ensuring Effective Organization of Public Administration in the Sphere”;

– Presidential Resolution No. PQ-171 of 31 May 2023 “On Measures to Ensure the Effective Organization of the Activities of the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change.” Second, leasing unused forest fund lands to legal entities and individuals for long-term use under public-private partnership conditions to establish new forests and medicinal plant plantations, and monitoring compliance with lease agreement requirements.

Third, exercising prosecutorial oversight over the proper implementation of forest monitoring, state forest accounting, and the state forest cadastre.

Fourth, monitoring compliance with the procedure established in the Law “On Specially Protected Natural Areas” of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding the organization of recreational zones on forest fund plots and the development of ecotourism by the State Committee for Tourism Development and the State Forestry Committee within their respective powers.

Fifth, identifying violations of the requirements for the use and protection of forests on state forest fund lands, and ensuring compliance with legislative acts during the review of cases related to such violations. It should be noted that although the adoption of the new edition of the Law “On Forests” has eliminated a number of existing problems, the necessity to introduce certain amendments regarding the leasing of lands belonging to this category still remained. Therefore, based on this need, in accordance with Article 14 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Amendments and Addenda to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Connection with Further Improving the Legal Framework of Corporate Relations,” adopted on 7 February 2025 under number URQ-1025, the words “state bodies, institutions, and enterprises” in the second part of Article 8 of the Law “On Forests” were replaced with the words “state bodies and institutions”. As a result, the practice of leasing such lands to enterprises was discontinued. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-30 dated 30 May 2025, issued within the framework of the nationwide project “Green Space” and aimed at continuing consistent reforms in the forest management system and expanding green areas, starting from 1 November 2025, forest fund land plots will be placed under special protection, and changes to their categories will be carried out in accordance with a decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Furthermore, by this decree, starting from 1 October 2025, the following mechanisms aimed

at increasing public participation in the implementation of the nationwide “Green Space” project, ensuring transparency on the “Green Space” electronic platform, and strengthening digitalization were introduced:

- Indicating specific locations where trees may be planted based on public initiative (district/city, street, coordinates of the land plot), water supply availability, opportunities for further care, and types of trees to be planted;

- Providing the public with online information—based on the principle of “tracking every penny spent”—about activities carried out within the nationwide “Green Space” project funded from the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- Displaying information about a person who has applied for permission to cut trees or shrubs, including details about the tree proposed for transplantation or cutting, the reason for transplantation (or cutting), its exact address, location, and accompanying photo and video materials;

- Introducing a system for recording saplings of trees and shrubs planted as compensation by individuals who illegally cut down or damage valuable species of trees and shrubs that do not belong to the forest fund;

- Requiring the continuous entry of information into the “Green Space” electronic platform regarding individuals and legal entities who illegally cut trees, details of such violations, and the measures taken against them. Before discussing the characteristics of prosecutorial supervision over the implementation of legal acts related to forests, water fund lands, reserve lands, residential areas, industrial zones, and other designated land categories, we believe it is necessary to first understand the essence and meaning of “prosecutorial supervision.” In this regard, legal scholars hold different views. For example, E.V. Kolenko emphasizes that prosecutorial supervision makes it possible to hold a guilty person accountable when the necessary grounds exist. Meanwhile, one of our young legal scholars, D.Sh. Ibragimov, evaluates prosecutorial supervision as an independent control function of the state and particularly notes that this institution is interpreted differently within the academic community. Russian scholar Yu.E. Vinokurov proposes that this institution is expressed through the application of prosecutorial supervision documents. Furthermore, A.B. Komilov provides an even broader definition, stating that “prosecutorial supervision manifests itself not only in identifying and eliminating violations of the law but also in taking measures to prevent them.” Although the Russian Federation possesses the world’s largest forest land fund—amounting to 1.2 billion hectares, which is nearly 46 percent of the total land fund of the Russian Federation—the forest land fund remains an important subject of supervision as defined in Article 21 of the Russian Federation’s Law “On the Prosecutor’s Office. Additionally, the tasks outlined within the framework of the “Forest Management Development Strategy,” approved by the Russian Government on 11 February 2021 under No. 312, as well as Articles 81–84 of the Russian Federation’s Forest Code, specify that federal and local state bodies and local self-government bodies must operate within their established powers, ensuring supervision and prevention of legal violations in this area. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, Articles 12–15 of the new edition of the Law “On Forests,” No. O’RQ-475 dated 16 April 2018, define the powers of state authorities in the fields of protecting forests, safeguarding them, increasing forest resources, regenerating and restoring them, improving

their productivity, and regulating their use. These authorities include the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Committee on Forestry of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Committee on Ecology and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and local governmental bodies. In our opinion, based on the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Prosecutor’s Office,” the prosecutor’s supervision over the implementation of legal regulations concerning forests, water resources, reserve lands, settlements, industrial and other designated lands consists of four main elements: First, the timely and comprehensive identification of violations of legal regulations regarding forests; Second, the protection, preservation, multiplication, repeated multiplication, restoration of forests, increasing their productivity, and identifying violations of the law in the use of forests and the conditions leading to such violations; Third, the prompt adoption of comprehensive legal measures that effectively ensure the elimination of identified legal violations, as well as holding the guilty parties accountable in accordance with the law; Fourth, conducting regular monitoring of forests to identify changes in the state of the state forest fund, assess them, and make forecasts, in order to prevent negative impacts on forests in a timely manner, in compliance with the procedure established by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Regarding foreign experience in forest protection, it can be seen that this experience is effective. For example, the United Kingdom’s Environment Agency (EA) was officially established in 1996 by combining the functions of several previous agencies (such as river management, waste regulation, and pollution control). The Agency, in addition to protecting the environment, regulating waste, controlling pollution, and managing water and river systems, also carries out the prevention of the misuse of forest resources in ways that are harmful to society, the state, and citizens. It conducts preliminary investigations to identify the guilty parties and bring them to justice, participates in court proceedings, and, within the framework of the law, issues licenses and permits, revokes them when necessary, supervises entrepreneurial activities, conducts monitoring, and submits proposals to state and regional authorities to prevent legal violations. The Agency also has the practice of sending parliamentary inquiries and participating in hearings on these matters. In France, the “French Biodiversity Agency” (Office français de la biodiversité, OFB) merged several previously separate agencies—responsible for water, aquatic environments, national parks, hunting, and wildlife protection. Within the OFB, the environmental police monitor laws related to forests, water, natural habitats, wild flora and fauna, hunting and fishing, and nature protection. When necessary, inspectors have the authority of the police and the legal right to identify and investigate situations such as damage in natural areas, hunting and fishing violations, harmful waste in nature, and illegal activities, and to participate in judicial proceedings. In our view, studying the experience of developed countries is of significant importance for Uzbekistan as well. An integrative approach involving the state, scientific institutions, local and public organizations, the private sector, and citizens plays a crucial role in the protection of natural resources and in improving prosecutorial supervision to prevent environmental violations as criminal offenses. Based on the above, it can be stated that in organizing prosecutorial supervision over the implementation of legal regulations regarding the use of forest fund lands, it is necessary to thoroughly study the following issues:

- Whether the land fund is being used effectively;

- The legality of the removal of land plots from the forest fund;

•Cases of unauthorized occupation of the forest fund and whether the responsible authorities have taken appropriate measures and steps to return the land fund. Regarding the effective use of forest fund lands, it is important to ensure the rational use of forest resources for designated purposes, the expansion (reconstruction) of forest areas according to existing legal regulations, the cultivation of seedlings, the collection of medicinal herbs, the allocation of pastures for livestock, and the provision of land for agricultural products. Legal documents and contracts should clearly specify rights and obligations, and the mechanisms by which authorities carry out management and supervision should be established. Additionally, the legal consequences of violating established procedures should be clearly outlined, with particular attention paid to provisions that could lead to different interpretations. The use of forest fund lands for designated purposes is considered a primary object of prosecutorial supervision, and the situations that need to be examined include the following:

- The use of forest enterprise land plots in accordance with the purposes specified in contracts;
- The leasing of unused forest fund lands through auctions or under public-private partnership agreements;
- Measures taken to prevent unauthorized use of forests and other violations of the established procedures for their use;
- The organization and development of interrelated activities within forest enterprises, including the cultivation of seedlings, collection of medicinal plants, beekeeping, fishing, livestock production, processing, and production of consumer goods;
- Compliance with fire safety regulations in forests;
- Measures taken to prevent the disposal of household and domestic waste in forest enterprise lands and border areas, and to prevent pollution of the natural environment;
- Measures taken to prevent the cutting or damaging of trees, shrubs, other plants, and saplings located on forest enterprise lands;
- The presence of illegal structures on forest enterprise lands temporarily allocated for use. When carrying out a supervisory activity, it is necessary to examine whether each departmental document of forest enterprises or contracts concluded with other entities comply with current regulatory and legal documents, and whether they are directed toward the fulfillment of the tasks established by law. Cases where forest enterprise lands are used for purposes other than those specified in the contract are addressed through proper monitoring procedures. According to Article 831 of the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan,

state control over the targeted use of land plots is not considered an inspection of the activities of business entities.

According to the Administrative Regulation on Leasing Forest Fund Land Plots through an Electronic Online Auction, approved by Resolution No. 674 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2023, forest management organizations acting as lessors must conduct quarterly monitoring of the fulfillment of lease agreements concluded for forest fund land plots.

During the monitoring process, the following issues are examined:

- compliance with the obligations specified in the lease agreement for the forest fund land plot;
- taking measures to fully preserve and increase existing trees, using the land strictly for its designated purpose, applying environmentally friendly production technologies, and preventing deterioration of the ecological situation in the area as a result of the lessee's activities;
- maintaining existing irrigation-melioration networks and engineering communications in working condition;
- implementing the set of measures provided for in environmental protection legislation;
- preventing illegal tree cutting and livestock grazing on the leased land;
- preventing unauthorized construction, avoiding changes to the land plot's designated specialization, ensuring timely payment of rent and other fees, and compliance with forestry legislation.

From this perspective, it is necessary to examine whether the relevant agronomic services of forest management organizations have conducted monitoring of land plots temporarily allocated to other entities, ensuring that they are used according to the purposes specified in the lease agreements, and whether appropriate measures were taken in response to detected violations.

State forestry bodies may lease unused forest fund lands to individuals and legal entities through an electronic online auction. Unused forest fund lands may be leased to individuals and legal entities based on an investment agreement or public-private partnership for a period of not less than three years and not more than forty-nine years.

The leasing of unused forest fund lands through auctions or under public-private partnership agreements is carried out in accordance with Resolution No. 674 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2023, On Measures to Improve Lease Relations in the Use of State Forest Fund Lands, and the Administrative Regulation on Leasing Forest Fund Land Plots through an Electronic Online Auction approved by it.

This regulation defines the procedure for preparing materials for placing forest fund land plots on the E-auction platform, organizing and conducting electronic online auctions, making settlements, formalizing lease agreements, amending them, and terminating them. According to the established procedure, the preparation, review, and approval of materials for leasing unused forest fund land plots to individuals and legal entities must be carried out through the "E-ijara" information system starting from January 1, 2024.

When studying cases of leasing unused forest fund land plots to individuals and legal entities, special attention must be paid to compliance with this procedure after January 1, 2024.

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